

EXPLORING THE LUNAR FAR SIDE AT TSIOLKOVSKIY CRATER. G. Tognon¹, R. Pozzobon² and M. Massironi^{1,2}, ¹Center of Studies and Activities for Space “G. Colombo”, University of Padova, Via Venezia 15, 35131, Padova (Italy), ²Department of Geosciences, University of Padova, Via Gradenigo 6, 35131, Padova (Italy).

Introduction: Nowadays, the ESA’s Heracles and NASA’s Artemis programs have laid the groundwork for resuming the robotic and human exploration of the Moon. Although their main target site is the lunar South Pole, other compelling sites should not be excluded a priori.

Here, we focus our attention on the less explored far side of the Moon, and in particular on the 180-km diameter Late Imbrian Tsiolkovskiy crater (20.4°S, 129.1°E).

What could make Tsiolkovskiy crater a possible future landing site for a rover-based exploration is its particularly smooth resurfaced crater floor formed by multiple eruptive events that led to the formation of one of the few mare exposures on the lunar far side [1, 2, 3]. The detection of pure anorthosite [4, 5] and olivine [6] on the central peak of the crater, moreover, could help in bringing new insights on the lunar crust origin and composition.

Data and methods: In order to perform a geological study of Tsiolkovskiy as potential landing site, the area has been geo-morphologically mapped by means of the ~100 m/pixel Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Wide Angle Camera [7] global mosaic together with the Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter and Kaguya Terrain Camera merged DEM with horizontal and vertical resolution respectively of ~59 m/pixel and 3-4 m [8]. A geo-spectral mapping, instead, has been performed on the Clementine UVVIS Warped Color Ratio mosaic with a resolution of ~200 m/pixel [9].

Results and descriptions:

Morphological mapping. In the area delimited by the rim of Tsiolkovskiy its was possible to distinguish three units ascribable to the crater floor, namely the well-preserved central peak rising ~3 km over a very smooth material characterized by a sharp boundary with respect to the adjacent hummocky material, and three units corresponding to the crater walls, namely the rough and collapsed material characterizing the crater rim in which it is possible to distinguish ponds of smooth material and steep scarps with slopes >40°. The upper panel of Fig. 1 shows the morphological mapping.

Spectral mapping. The false color band ratioed composite image allowed to distinguish several units characterized by different colors ascribable to compositional variegations which are mostly correlated to the morphological units. In particular, it is possible to discern the yellow-orange basaltic compositions corresponding to the smooth crater floor opposed the blue hues of anorthosites, norites and troc-

Fig. 1: Morphological mapping (upper panel) and spectral mapping (bottom panel).

tolites correlated to the central peak and the steep scarps. The hummocky floor, the rim of Tsiolkovskiy and its smooth ponds, instead, are characterized by the red color of the mature highland soil. The spectral mapping is shown in the bottom of Fig. 1.

Landing site analysis. A high resolution mapping performed on a Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Narrow Angle Camera [7] mosaic (~0.5 m/pixel but here scaled at 3 m/pixel) allows the planning of broad traverses for a rover-based exploration from potential landing ellipses. Along the traverses, the rover will have the possibility to come across different basaltic soils generated by distinct eruptions and to collect materials in proximity of sites where olivine and purest anorthosite have been detected. The location of the traverses along steep scarps, moreover, could allow the analysis of collapsed material that otherwise would not be possible to sample. In addition, the results of the investigation of potential deep structures hidden underneath Tsiolkovskiy performed by means of Kaguya Lunar Radar Sounder data could be integrated in the rover traverses for further in situ analysis.

Conclusions: The hereby presented data are the current results of the geo-morphological and geo-spectral mappings performed for the geologic characterization of the lunar Tsiolkovskiy crater. Its morphology and composition provide at the same

time an optimal and safe place to land and a scientifically interesting area as possible landing site for a rover-based exploration.

References: [1] Whitford-Stark J. L. and Hawke B. R. (1982) *LPSC XXXIII*, 861-862. [2] Pieters C. M. and Tompkins S. (1999) *JGR*, 104, 21935-21949. [3] Mouginis-Mark P. J. and Boyce J. M. (2017) *LPS XLVIII*, Abstract #1206. [4] Ohtake M. et al. (2009) *Nature*, 461, 236-241. [5] Lemelin M. et al. (2015) *JGR: Planets*, 120, 869-8878. [6] Corley L. M. et al. (2018) *Icarus*, 300, 287-304. [7] Robinson M. S. et al. (2010) *Space Sci. Rev.*, 150, 81-124. [8] Barker M. K. et al. (2016) *Icarus*, 273, 346-355. [9] Lucey P. G. et al. (2000) *JGR*, 105, 20377-20386.